

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PARLIAMENTARY FUNCTIONS IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract: Parliamentarism is positioned as a new vector in developing scientific approaches to public administration. The aim of the study is a comparative analysis of the role and functions of parliament in the public administration system. The article examines the evolution of the studied issue, including the institutionalisation of the concept of parliamentarism in Ukraine. The role and place of parliament in the state power and public administration system are identified, and its functions as the main component of popular representation are determined. Contemporary trends in the transformation of parliamentarism are analysed. The current tasks of parliament in the public administration system are specified. It is substantiated that parliamentarism represents a unique system of public administration that endows parliament with essential functions concerning representative democracy. Variations of models for effectively implementing popular representation in public administration and state-building processes are explored. The dynamics of the phenomenon of political culture are studied from the perspective of ensuring societal consolidation and unity. The article proves that parliamentarism is positioned as an interdisciplinary vector of a complex socio-political phenomenon that reflects the system of political power organisation in the state. The competencies and functional standards of parliament in the overall system of public administration implementation are highlighted. It is proven that the practical, functional realisation of parliament in public administration should include mechanisms to mitigate corruption risks. The study represents the significance of parliamentarism in the modern progress of the public administration system in implementing popular representation based on transparency, openness, and active Euro-integration development.

Keywords: Public administration, Parliamentarism, Parliament, Parity, Democracy, Representative bodies, Civil society, Women's political and managerial leadership, Political culture, EU, Democracy

1 Introduction

Recently, the concept of the place and role of parliament in the public administration system has undergone significant changes. Primarily, the phenomenon of parliamentarism has transformed from a theoretical formation into an objective, practical reality of the functioning of the public power system. In general, parliamentarism is positioned globally as one of the essential attributes of a democratic state.

Moreover, the current stage of societal development is characterised by a global democratic crisis. In this context, parliamentarism is viewed as a guarantor of effective and practically valuable democratic representation. Furthermore, the role of parliamentarism as an institution of public administration is steadily increasing, synergising aspects of representative and legislative power.

Thus, parliament plays a unique role in the system of public administration, where the synergy of state administration institutions, civil society, and local self-government finds practical expression in the formation of a system of social relations at various levels – higher, central, regional, and local – by their assigned powers and functions. This issue is particularly relevant to society's growing demands for integration into forming state-level management decisions.

2 Literature review

In studying the role, place, and functionality of parliament in the public administration system, particular academic interest is found in the works of Hoshovska and Reiterovych (2022), Dudko (2022), Karmazina (2020), and Cherkas (2021). Several researchers (Reiterovych & Parfeniuk, 2021; Danylenko et al., 2022; Ortina et al., 2023) pay particular attention to the definition and essence of parliament as a representative body of authority, examining its institutional capacity and primary practical significance in a democratic society.

Certain scholars (Semenets-Orlova et al., 2022; Kortukova et al., 2023) focus their research on the phenomenon of parliamentarism in the context of institutional support for the interaction between government bodies and civil society. Foreign scholars have made a significant contribution to the development of this area of research (Wright, 2019; Onyango, 2020; Rozenberg, 2020), whose publications focus on the impact of state transformation on public administration, the definitions of parliament, parliamentarism, and parliamentary democracy, as well as unresolved political contexts of public governance.

At the same time, Androniceanu (2021) and Heath (2020) emphasise the importance of transparency in public administration in ensuring proper democratic governance, studying the specifics of public administration development in the public sector, and investigating the interaction between public administration and liberal state policy. Nevertheless, despite scholars' achievements, research on the position of parliament within the modern public administration system amid active societal dynamics and the Euro-integration orientation of Ukraine's post-war democratic development is still fragmented.

The article aims to provide a comparative analysis of parliament's role and functions in the public administration system.

3 Research methods

The research methodology is composed of several contemporary scientific methods, including the use of:

- the systemic method, which allows the study of the phenomenon of public administration as a systemic entity, and parliamentarism as its integral subsystem, functioning based on established theoretical views and effective practices;
- the method of retrospective analysis, which is grounded in the concepts of the theory and practice of parliamentarism during its formation and contemporary development;
- comparative analysis allows the study of the institutionalisation and specific development of parliamentarism in Ukraine, taking into account the practical experience of other countries.

4 Results

It is crucial today to reflect on and integrate practical concepts for developing and improving parliamentarism, driven by the dynamics of societal needs and development strategies. The most significant concepts today include:

- the concept of institutionalism, which positions parliament as a leading state institution endowed with constituent, representative-coordinating, budgetary, and legislative functions;
- the concept of the "service state", which envisions the transformation of parliament on clientelist principles;
- the concept of public governance determines the transformation from public administration to public

governance (Reiterovych & Parfeniuk, 2021; Danylenko et al., 2022; Ortina et al., 2023).

The foundation of all these approaches is the traditional concept of the priority of popular representation, which gains particular significance in periods of active global dynamics. Widespread representation practically expresses local and state societal interests, manifested through authorised governmental bodies (Semenets-Orlova et al., 2022; Kortukova et al., 2023).

This phenomenon is positioned not only as an attribute of a democratic state but also as a subjective right of the people to representation, as established in Article 38, Part 1, Article 136, Part 1, and Article 140, Part 4 of the Constitution of Ukraine (Reiterovych, 2022). The conceptual foundations of popular representation in the form of parliamentarism are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Conceptual framework of people's representation in public administration

Conceptual framework	Features
Institutional	- conditioned by the sovereignty of the people; - ensuring the supremacy of human and civil rights and freedoms; - the possibility of establishing representative authorities that embody the people's will and are responsible to the people
Functional	- conditioned by the content of the activities of representative bodies of power at different levels (state, local); - provision of legislative acts on democracy; - systematic professional training of personnel for work in representative bodies of power
Ideological	- the idea of social justice; - ensuring conditions for fair governance of society and the state; - complexity of study and maximum consideration of the interests of society

Source: compiled by the author based on (Hoshovska, 2022)

Parliament represents the institutional embodiment of the people's power, endowed with the authority to make legislative decisions on behalf of the people. Parliament determines the vector of the state's socio-economic development, the optimisation of societal activities, and the strengthening of various forms of cooperation (Wright, 2019; Onyango, 2020; Rozenberg, 2020).

The phenomenon of parliamentarism should be considered in its dual nature, as parliamentarism is both a particular system of state organisation and a specific political institution (Androniceanu, 2021; Heath, 2020). The functions of the first facet are determined by the leading role of parliament in establishing and developing relations of social justice, forming the most representative mechanism of public power in the context of citizens' interests, making state decisions, and ensuring the practical exercise of popular sovereignty. At the same time, as a specific political institution, parliamentarism creates conditions for the active development of local self-government, promotes the expansion of society's political participation in public administration, and initiates the broadening of the communication process between the people and the state (Reiterovych & Parfeniuk, 2021; Danylenko et al., 2022; Ortina et al., 2023).

Thus, the role of parliament in public administration is the combination of the functional and substantial characteristics of the state structure aimed at minimising the distance between the government and society (Wright, 2019; Onyango, 2020; Rozenberg, 2020). Parliament must ensure the realisation of the people's interests within the legislative framework, thereby intensifying the development of statehood in general and the participatory concept of public administration in particular. The parliament sets the vector for developing society's subsystems, shaping public policy (Semenets-Orlova et al., 2022; Kortukova et al., 2023).

It should be noted that the definitions of "parliament" and "parliamentarism" are not synonymous, although they are interrelated. This is the differentiation of power and representation within the cooperation framework in the "parliament-civil society" system (Reiterovych, 2022; Dudko, 2022; Karmazina, 2020). The effectiveness of this interaction creates the prerequisites for increasing the publicity of politics, ensuring transparency and openness of management processes, stabilising socio-political life, and actively contributing to the growth of trust in the parliament (Androniceanu, 2021; Heath, 2020). As a political institution of parliamentarism, the parliament determines the pace of expanding society's political participation in the transformation of management processes, as

it acts as a mediator between the state and the structural elements of society (Kryvoshein et al., 2022).

Today, the development of parliamentarism is characterised by several challenges, including the value-based societal attitude towards parliamentarism at all levels of public administration and the parliament's compliance with international standards and requirements. Parliamentarism preserves national traditions in various countries differently (Wright, 2019; Onyango, 2020; Rozenberg, 2020). In this context, it is necessary to consider the requirements for national and international parliamentarism. Popular representation, in this case, is seen as the foundation for the functioning and development of a democratic society, the basis of the constitutional order of a democratic state, which ensures the exercise of the people's power through authorised bodies (Reiterovych, 2022; Dudko, 2022; Karmazina, 2020).

Within the modern concept of popular representation, the essential prerequisites for its successful implementation are identified, including:

- the practical implementation of the people's sovereignty within the framework of popular representation;
- the exercise of state power through popular representation, complementary to the demands and needs of modern society;
- the reflection and implementation of societal interests by famous representatives at the national level rather than those of a specific component of society;
- variability of mechanisms for forming representative bodies while ensuring democratic free elections;
- the permissibility of a collegial component in representative bodies (Semenets-Orlova et al., 2022; Kortukova et al., 2023).

Global challenges to the development of domestic parliamentarism are focused on the strategy of "new regionalism" – a concept of political, socio-economic, and cultural integration that requires the transformation of professional training for parliamentarians and parliamentary staff (Androniceanu, 2021; Heath, 2020). The strategy involves changing the behaviour of political leaders for the successful implementation of new trends in international relations, including intensifying democratisation processes at the national level, eliminating ideological barriers to inter-parliamentary cooperation, and promoting globalisation and international, regional cooperation at a new level (Reiterovych & Parfeniuk, 2021; Danylenko et al., 2022; Ortina et al., 2023).

Overall, among the global trends and challenges of modern parliamentarism in the public administration system, it is necessary to highlight:

- the intensification of the parliament's role in government formation;

Figure 1. Results of the survey 'Citizens and Parliament: Trust, Interaction and Openness under Martial Law'
Source: compiled by the author based on (RADA survey, 2024)

As shown in Figure 1, the level of public trust in parliament has significantly decreased. To optimise the situation in the context of Ukraine, the following priority trends in the development of parliamentarism within the public administration system are highlighted:

- the creation of targeted information and communication support for the functioning of popular representation;
- intensifying the role and significance of representative democracy as a "universal value";
- professionalising aspects of parliamentary activity;
- the dynamic of a hybrid model of interest representation in the state should synergise formal and informal political practices, facilitating the implementation of the neo-corporatist strategy (Wright, 2019; Onyango, 2020; Rozenberg, 2020).

In Ukraine, financial-industrial groups, which actively use political means of influence and gradually integrate into power structures, exert significant influence on the socio-economic and political processes in the country. The neo-corporatist model envisages the formation of an active civil society capable of effectively representing and defending its interests (Reiterovych & Parfeniuk, 2021; Danylenko et al., 2022; Ortina et al., 2023). It involves practical tools for ensuring functional interests in the interaction between business and politics. This is particularly relevant for Ukraine, which needs to complete the formation of an effective institutional system based on improved, clear rules and norms of self-regulation.

Slow but steady transformation in this direction is facilitated by specific institutional changes, including the expansion of the functions of civil society organisations, decentralisation, the start of judicial reform, a shift in foreign policy priorities, and civil service reform (Androniceanu, 2021; Heath, 2020). In the future, efforts should be focused on intensifying the influence of representative bodies of state power (Semenets-Orlova et al., 2022; Kortukova et al., 2023). In this case, the priorities should be lobbying for public interests in the public sphere and integrating the principles of practical popular sovereignty.

The role of parliament in Ukraine's public administration system during the post-war period will rapidly grow in the direction of developing a democratic society characterised by a high level of political and legal culture (Reiterovych, 2022; Dudko, 2022; Karmazina, 2020). A clear differentiation between legislative and executive functions and the dominant position of parliament

- the general trend of declining trust in parliament (Figure 1);
- absenteeism;
- the need for structural transformation of modern parliaments (Reiterovych, 2022; Dudko, 2022; Karmazina, 2020).

as a state body of popular representation characterises such a society. Pan-European values concerning rights and freedoms – democracy, the rule of law, respect for human dignity, equality, and the prioritisation of human rights – highlight the directions for the further progress of parliamentarism in Ukraine's public administration system.

5 Discussion

Several contemporary authors explore the role of parliament in the functioning and development of the public administration system. In particular, Demir (2023) positions the relationship between politics and administration in the context of normative and empirical approaches. The scholar's specific research areas encompass the connections, similarities, and differences between these two spheres of governance.

Researchers Hassan et al. (2022) suggest establishing independent electoral committees, implementing and improving parliamentary service legislation by international standards, and expanding the powers of the opposition. The researchers pay special attention to the need to incorporate sustainable development goals into the parliamentary reform agenda, which is essential to support parliamentarians in effectively carrying out their duties. As Hassan et al. (2022) noted, such an approach contributes to the maximum representation of public interests within parliamentary formations.

At the same time, Rocabert et al. (2019) study the activities of international parliamentary institutions, which have become an established feature of international politics. They focus mainly on creating parliamentary bodies that align with the demands of the globally developed community. According to scholars, the implementation of international standards in the public administration systems of developing countries should be accompanied by a transformation in approaches to the functioning of parliamentarism.

Several contemporary scholars (Prior, 2022; Selinger, 2019) examine the specifics of public engagement in parliamentary work, aiming at the maximum representation of public interests, ensuring the openness and transparency of public administration processes, and the practical implementation of democratic principles in societal functioning.

Furthermore, Hoshovska and Kuibida (2018), and Hoshovska (2021, 2024) explores the specifics of the implementation of representative power in Ukraine's state-building process, focusing on advancing the modern formation of political culture

to ensure unity and consolidation of society. The scholar argues for the need to optimise strategic development priorities for Ukrainian parliamentarism in the context of globalisation and analyses political leadership in representative power amid global challenges.

Kreidenko (2022), studying the globalisation challenges of the future governance system, considers parliament not only a legislative body but also a symbol of modern democracy. The author believes that parliament's relationship with other political institutions helps to formulate a country's constitutional regime.

At the same time, Hoshovska and Kravchuk (2024) study the potential of artificial intelligence in public administration. The scholars emphasise that the development of the foundations of digital law is highly relevant today to ensure the integrity of legislative regulation. The researchers analyse models of civil law regulation through artificial intelligence tools, focusing on the issues of artificial intelligence's legal subjectivity, including aspects of responsibility and risks.

Despite significant scholarly achievements, the issue of rethinking the role of parliament in the public administration system in light of the promising development of post-war Ukraine requires further scientific exploration.

6 Conclusion

Parliamentarism represents a specific system of public administration where the parliament holds a priority role, democratic significance, and legislative functionality. Parliament has a unique role in the system of public governance, where the synergy of state administration institutions, civil society, and local self-government finds practical expression in forming a system of social relations at various levels – the highest, central, regional, and local – by the powers and functions assigned to them.

Among the global trends and challenges of modern parliamentarism in the public administration system, it is essential to note the intensification of the parliament's role in government formation; the general trend of declining trust in parliament; absenteeism; and the need for structural transformation of contemporary parliaments.

The principles of effective implementation of parliamentary functions within the public administration system include ensuring the unhindered sovereignty of the people through popular representation; representatives expressing the general societal interests of the entire population rather than specific parts of it; the collegial composition of governmental bodies; and the implementation of state power, which is as complementary to societal needs as possible through popular representation. Acceptable, in this context, is the variability of mechanisms for forming representative bodies, while the dominance of free elections remains unconditional.

Modern trends in the development of parliamentarism in Ukraine include the integration of international democratic and humanistic principles of public administration. This outlined process in the context of representative democracy requires the formation of an appropriate information and communication platform to support and implement the ideas of popular representation, as well as the intensification of the role of representative democracy as a “universal value” and on this basis, the creation of representative government bodies. Further professionalisation of parliamentary activities is necessary for Ukraine's post-war development and Euro-integration vector.

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